

This repository is under review for potential modification in compliance with Administration directives.

Learn About RADx Data Hub

[Home](#) > [About](#)

About RADx Data Hub

The NIH Rapid Acceleration of Diagnostics (RADx) Data Hub is a secure cloud-based platform, enabling researchers to access curated, de-identified datasets and analytic tools to support innovation in disease diagnostics and public health efforts.

Designed to promote researcher collaboration and accelerate scientific discovery, the RADx Data Hub seeks to understand public health and disease

morbidity and mortality disparities, while supporting innovations in the development, commercialization, and implementation of diagnostic technologies through de-identified data and algorithms.

In the Data Hub, researchers can collaborate with one another, explore and analyze harmonized data, apply AI and machine learning tools, and share their findings to advance evidence-based diagnostic solutions, strengthening overall health system resilience.

RADx Coordinating and Data Collection Centers

Rapidly sharing RADx data and results empowers the scientific community to conduct secondary analyses, advances diagnostic innovation, and addresses disease detection and prevention concerns, ultimately leading to new diagnostic technologies. The RADx Data Hub partners with and supports the

following RADx Coordinating and Data Collection Centers (C)DCCs, which collect and share diagnostic research data and technologies:

RADx Tech

The RADx Tech accelerates development, validation, and commercialization of innovative point-of-care, home-based, and clinical laboratory diagnostic technologies. RADx Tech has expanded the NIH's National Institute of Biomedical Imaging and Bioengineering (NIIBIB) Point-of-Care Technologies Research Network (POCTRN) leveraging expertise from technology innovators, clinical testing, regulatory affairs, entrepreneurs, and business leaders. Learn more at <https://www.nibib.nih.gov/programs/radx-tech-program>

RADx-UP

RADx-UP seeks to understand disease diagnostic morbidity and mortality disparities to reduce health concerns for vulnerable populations. These researchers collaborate with community members to unite public health and diagnostics, improving community-level outcomes. Learn more at <https://radx-up.org/>

RADx-rad

RADx-rad drives the discovery of bold, new, and unconventional disease diagnostic approaches including rapid detection devices and home-based testing technologies. This work may also lead to new ways of identifying diseases, promoting faster diagnoses in the future. Learn more at <https://www.radxrad.org/>

RADx DHT

RADx DHT develops digital health solutions, such as user-friendly smartphone apps, wearable devices, and software, supporting real-time health monitoring, disease tracking, and data-sharing to support public health-related decision-making. Learn more at <https://rapids.ll.mit.edu/>

About RADx Data Hub Partners

A partnership of Stanford University (Stanford), Booz Allen Hamilton, and the Renaissance Computing Institute (RENCI) assists the NIH with three key aspects of the RADx Data Hub:

- **Data Hub Development:** Develop and enhance the Data Hub functions that store, share, and provide data analysis and

utilization capabilities ([Booz Allen Hamilton](#))

- **Data Management:** Translate proposed standards for data and metadata into computational form, validate data quality, and enable greater use of common data elements, standardization, and harmonization ([Stanford](#))
- **Program Management:** Establish and maintain effective cross-disciplinary program management, including technical development, data coordinating center connectivity, researcher engagement, and training ([RENCI](#))

[RADx Data Hub](#)

[Need Support?](#)

[Related Websites](#)

[RADx Initiative](#)

[Website Policies](#)

[User Code of Conduct](#)

[About](#)

[Frequently Asked Questions](#)

[Study Explorer](#)

[News](#)

[Resource Center](#)

[RADx Programs](#)

[Office of Data Science Strategy](#)

[ClinicalTrials.gov](#)

[dbGaP](#)

[Accessibility](#)

[Privacy Policy](#)

[HHS Vulnerability Disclosure](#)

[Disclaimers](#)

[No Fear Act](#)

[Freedom of Information Act](#)

Connect with Us:

